

Original article

Potential Protective Effect of *Panax ginseng* (roots) against Minerals and Lipid Profile Changes in Adult Male Rabbits administered with Stannous Chloride

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ARTICLE INFO

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ABSTRACT

Received: 27-01-2023

Accepted: 21-02-2023

Published: 23-02-2023

Keywords. Stannous Chloride, *Panax ginseng*, minerals, lipid profile.

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Background and aims. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the potential protective effects of *Panax ginseng* (*P. ginseng*). Changes in levels of some minerals and lipid profiles induced by stannous chloride (SnCl_2) in male rabbits were studied. **Methods.** Sixteen rabbits were randomly divided into four equal groups (each four rabbits). The first group was used as a control and received an equivalent volume of corn oil alone. The second group was used to study the effect of *P. ginseng* (100 mg/kg body weight) and the third group was used to study the effect of SnCl_2 (20 mg/kg body weight). The fourth group was used to study the effect of *P. ginseng* plus SnCl_2 . Animals were treated orally daily for 10 weeks. **Results.** *P. ginseng* alone caused a non-significant increase in levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL), sodium (Na^+), Magnesium (Mg^{+2}), and Zinc (Zn^{+2}). Treatment with *P. ginseng* alone caused a non-significant decrease in levels of cholesterol, phosphorus (Po_4^-), and calcium (Ca^{+2}). *P. ginseng* alone causes a significant decrease in levels of triglycerides (TG) and high-density lipoprotein (HDL). Overall means indicated that treatment with SnCl_2 caused a non-significant increase in levels of LDL, Ca^{+2} , and Mg^{+2} . The same treatment caused a significant increase in the level of (Zn^{+2}). Meanwhile, treatment with SnCl_2 caused a non-significant decrease in levels of cholesterol, Po_4^- and Na^+ . This treatment caused a decrease in levels of TG and HDL. The combination of *P. ginseng* and SnCl_2 minimized the effect of SnCl_2 in all previous parameters to be close to control values. **Conclusion.** The results of the present study convincingly demonstrated that SnCl_2 exposure resulted in varying degrees of effect in values of some minerals and lipid profiles. Thus *P. ginseng* may be helpful to combat SnCl_2 -associated sufferings in human as well as animals.

Cite this article. Abuajaila A, Ali M, Khaled F, Othman O. Potential Protective Effect of *Panax ginseng* (roots) against Minerals and Lipid Profile Changes in Adult Male Rabbits administered with Stannous Chloride. *Alq J Med App Sci.* 2023;6(1):65-73.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7665945>

INTRODUCTION

Tin (Sn) is a natural element within the crust of the earth. Tin compounds have been used extensively in a variety of human activities. Tin can combine with chemicals such as chlorine, sulfur, and oxygen to form inorganic tin compounds such as stannous chloride, stannous sulfide, and stannic oxide. These inorganic tin compounds are used in a diversity of industrial processes, including glass toughening, a base for color, catalysts, perfume, soap stabilizers, and dental cryogenic agents [1]. Sn also combines with carbon to form organotin compounds such as (dibutyltin, tributyltin, and triphenyltin), which are used in the manufacture of food packages, plastic pipes, plastics, paints, and pest repellents [2]. Humans are exposed to stannous chloride (SnCl_2) in packaged foods, soft drinks, biocides, and dentifrices. Since SnCl_2 is widely used in the production of food cans and beverage packaging, many studies have focused on its toxic effects [3,4]. SnCl_2 induces changes in many biochemical parameters in experimental animals [5].

A previous study showed that the administration of SnCl_2 to male rats caused a significant increase in calcium levels

[6]. In addition, various studies have mainly shown that excessive dietary tin reduces essential serum minerals such as iron, copper, zinc, calcium, and selenium, and reduces antioxidant activity, mainly in the liver [7,8]. Additionally, previous studies mentioned that administration with SnCl₂ caused an increase in the levels of plasma total lipid (TL), cholesterol, triglyceride (TG), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), glucose, urea, and total bilirubin, while the levels of plasma high-density lipoprotein (HDL), total protein (TP), albumin (A) and globulin (G) were decreased [5].

Medicinal plants generally contain compounds that are useful in the treatment or administration of diseases in animals and humans [9]. Ginseng has been used as a panacea for over 2,000 years and was believed to promote longevity [10]. *Panax ginseng* is one of the most widely used herbal medicines and is reported to have a wide range of therapeutic and pharmacological applications [11]. The main bioactive components of ginseng are triterpenoid saponin glycosides, also called ginsenosides [12,13]. Ginsenosides are the main pharmacologically active components of *P. ginseng*, and appear to be involved in most of the activities of *P. ginseng*, including vasorelaxation, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer [14]. These properties of ginseng are thought to provide many beneficial effects against organ damage [13].

P. ginseng may play a protective role by enhancing liver enzymatic activity and restoring biochemical parameters against carbon tetrachloride-induced liver injury in rats [15]. Treatment with *P. ginseng* resulted in a decrease in serum concentrations of triglyceride, total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein-cholesterol, and low-density lipoprotein-cholesterol in rats [16]. Therefore, the present study was conducted to determine the ability of *P. ginseng* to minimize the detrimental effects of stannous chloride on lipid profile concentrations and mineral levels in male rabbits.

METHODS

Tested compounds

SnCl₂ was brought from the chemistry department, faculty of science, Omar Al-Mukhtar University (20 mg/ml body weight every other day). *P. ginseng* (Root powder) was purchased from a local pharmacy, with a dose of 100 mg/ml body weight every other day for 12 weeks. Sixteen male New Zealand white rabbits (6 months old) were individually housed in cages and weighed weekly throughout 10 weeks' experimental period.

Study design

Sixteen mature male rabbits were randomly divided into four equal groups (n=4 for each group) as follows:

Group I: Rabbits were used as control and received an equivalent of 1 ml of the vehicle (corn oil) alone by oral gavage twice per week for 10 successive weeks.

Group II: In this group rabbits were given oral administration of *P. ginseng* with a dose of 100 mg/kg/day [17].

Group III: These rabbits received orally with SnCl₂ 20 mg/kg/day [5].

Group IV: These rabbits were administered orally with a combination of SnCl₂ and *P. ginseng*.

Rabbits were orally administered their respective doses for 3 months. Blood samples were collected from the ear vein of all animals every week throughout the experimental period and at the end of the experiment. Each blood sample was placed in a dry clean centrifuge tube and then centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 revolutions per minute (rpm) to separate the serum for determining the lipids profile concentration, minerals, and electrolytes level.

Assay of a lipid profile

Total cholesterol was determined according to the method of [18], and triglycerides (TG) by the method [19]. High-density lipoprotein (HDL) and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) were assayed by using the methods of [20].

Assay of electrolytes

The levels of Sodium (Na⁺), Potassium (K⁺), and Magnesium (Mg⁺²) were measured using an automatic electrolyte analyzer (EasyLyte from MediaCorp, USA). Serum phosphorus was determined by phosphomolybdate UV endpoint [21], using an Ammonium Molybdate Diagnostic kit, and the level of calcium (Ca⁺²) was measured using the method of [22]. Also, serum was assayed to determine the concentration of Zn⁺² according to the method of [23].

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained were expressed as mean ±SEM. The significant differences were assessed by one-way ANOVA and Tukey test. After the detection of the normal distribution of the data and appropriate P-values, less than 0.05 is considered significant.

RESULTS

The mean values of Cholesterol, Triglycerides (TG), Low-density lipoprotein (LDL), High-density Lipoprotein (HDL) throughout 10 weeks of the experimental period were shown in (Table 1). Treatment with *P. ginseng* /SnCl₂ alone caused a significant decrease in levels of (TG and HDL) and a non-significant decrease in levels of cholesterol compared to the control group (Table 1). On the other hand, treatment with *P. ginseng*/ SnCl₂ alone caused a non-significant increase in levels of LDL compared to the control group (Table 1). Treatment with the combination of *P. ginseng* and SnCl₂ retained levels of cholesterol, TG, LDH, HDL, and LDL close to the values of the control group (Table 1). All these changes started from the second week of the experiment as shown in (1-4 Figures).

Table 1. Illustrate the levels of plasma lipid and lipoprotein profiles of male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, SnCl₂, and their combination at end of the experiment.

Lipids (mg/dl)	Experimental groups			
	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV
Cholesterol	78.2±10.47 ^a	59.00±5.75 ^a	52.11±7.44 ^a	62.22±7.43 ^a
P. values	Groups= 0.132		Weeks= 0.161	
TG	63.22±3.71 ^a	41.44±1.66 ^c	46.11±3.63 ^b	57.33±4.26 ^{ab}
P. values	Groups= 0.000		Weeks= 0.738	
LDL	63.33±3.95 ^a	72.22±5.23 ^a	72.11±4.96 ^a	60.22 ±7.31 ^a
P. values	Groups= 0.310		Weeks= 0.106	
HDL	48.39±5.76 ^a	38.56±1.77 ^{ab}	35.44±1.18 ^b	37.22±0.99 ^{ab}
P. values	Groups= 0.027		Weeks= 0.014	

Values are expressed as means ± SEM; n = 4 for each treatment group. Mean values within a row not sharing common superscript letters (a, b, c) were significantly different, p<0.05

Figure 1. Biweekly values of Cholesterol (Mean± SEM) in male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, SnCl₂ and their combination.

Figure 2. Biweekly values of Triglycerides (TG) (Mean± SEM) in male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, SnCl₂ and their combination

Figure 3. Biweekly values of LDL (Mean ± SEM) in male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, SnCl_2 and their combination

Figure 4. Biweekly values of HDL (Mean ± SEM) in male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, SnCl_2 , and their combination

Treatment with SnCl_2 resulted in a significant increase in the level of Zn^{+2} and a non-significant increase in Ca^{+2} and Mg^{+2} compared to the control group (Table 2). The values of Po_4^- and Na^{+2} were decreased in SnCl_2 alone treated group (Table 2). On the other hand, the present study indicated that treatment with *P. ginseng* alone had a non-significant decrease level of Po_4^- and Ca^{+2} , while the levels of Na^{+2} and Mg^{+2} increased without significant difference and a significant increase in the level of Zn^{+2} in male rabbits (Table 2). *P. ginseng* minimized the effect of SnCl_2 to be close to control values. All these changes started in the second week of the experiment as shown in (5-9 Figures).

Table 2. Illustrate the levels of minerals in male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, SnCl_2 , and their combination at end of the experiment

Parameter	Experimental groups			
	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV
PO_4^- (mg/dl)	6.378±0.35 ^a	5.767±0.50 ^a	5.711±0.30 ^a	6.178±0.41 ^a
P. values	Groups= 0.579		Weeks= 0.006	
Na^+ (mEq/l)	149.67±5.16 ^a	150.33±7.05 ^a	145.33±2.82 ^a	147.33±5.72 ^a
P. values	Groups= 0.910		Weeks= 0.020	
Ca^{+2} (mg/dl)	10.022±0.24 ^a	9.667±0.24 ^a	10.322±0.24 ^a	9.978±0.19 ^a
P. values	Groups= 0.267		Weeks= 0.482	
Mg^{+2} (mg/dl)	2.322±0.17 ^a	2.544±0.18 ^a	2.900±0.12 ^a	2.767±0.13 ^a
P. values	Groups= 0.054		Weeks= 0.196	
Zn^{+2} (mg/dl)	155.7±19.43 ^b	184.1±11.17 ^{ab}	234.44±9.53 ^a	178.7±28.7 ^{ab}
P. values	Groups= 0.040		Weeks= 0.000	

Values are expressed as means ± SEM; n = 4 for each treatment group. Mean values within a row not sharing common superscript letters (a, b, c) were significantly different, p<0.05

Figure 5. Biweekly values of PO_4^- (Mean± SEM) in male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, $SnCl_2$ and their combination

Figure 6. Biweekly values of Na^+ (Mean± SEM) in male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, $SnCl_2$ and their combination

Figure 7. Biweekly values of Ca^{+2} (Mean± SEM) in male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, $SnCl_2$ and their combination

Figure 8. Biweekly values of Mg^{+2} (Mean \pm SEM) in male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, $SnCl_2$ and their combination

Figure 9. Biweekly values of Zn^{+2} (Mean \pm SEM) in male rabbits treated with *P. ginseng*, $SnCl_2$ and their combination.

DISCUSSION

Humans are exposed to $SnCl_2$ by the consumption of food, especially packaged food, and soft drinks, which are considered the main source of inorganic forms of tin [24]. Therefore, several laboratory studies have focused on the toxic effects of $SnCl_2$ [3, 4]. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the potential protective effects of *P. ginseng*, and their combination after 10 weeks against lipid profile concentration and levels of some minerals (Na^+ , Ca^{+2} , Mg^{+2} , Po_4^- and Zn^{+2}) of male rabbits induced by $SnCl_2$.

Changes in serum cholesterol and TG levels indicate disturbances in lipid metabolism. The current study found that treatment with *P. ginseng* or $SnCl_2$ alone led to lower TG, HDL, and cholesterol levels compared to the control group. On the other hand, the administration with *P. ginseng* or $SnCl_2$ alone increased the levels of LDL compared to the control group. A previous study showed that the level of lipids such as TG, total cholesterol, HDL and LDL were decreased in the serum of rats as a result of treatment with *P. ginseng* [16, 25]. These observations were not in agreement with a previous study that found $SnCl_2$ increased the levels of plasma total lipid (TL), cholesterol, TG, LDL and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), While, the level of plasma HDL was decreased [5]. These alterations, in lipid profile, can be due to oxidative stress resulting from an imbalance of the prooxidant/antioxidant ratio, thus inducing tissue damage. Increased oxidation potential within the cell milieu promotes cholesterol synthesis, absorption, and distribution, and reduces the conversion of cholesterol to bile acids [26]. This leads to an increase or decrease in serum lipid levels in the body. As an alternative explanation, increases in plasma lipids with $SnCl_2$ administration indicate a loss of membrane integrity [27].

P. ginseng also lowered serum TG and cholesterol levels, according to several researchers [25,28,29]. Ginseng saponins can partially restore LDL biosynthesis in fowl fed a high-cholesterol diet [30]. The solubilizing activity of saponin may aid in the elimination of fat from circulation. Results from the current study showed that treatment with *P. ginseng* alone resulted in a decreased level of Po_4^- and Ca^{+2} . While the levels of Na^{+2} , Zn^{+2} and Mg^{+2} were increased in the serum of male rabbits. On the other hand, $SnCl_2$ administration increased the levels of Zn^{+2} , Ca^{+2} and Mg^{+2} , and decreased the values of Po_4^- and Na^{+2} compared to the control group. These observations are not in agreement with the previous study

that indicated Fe, Cu, and Zn²⁺ status was influenced by dietary Sn concentrations lower than 50 mg/kg causing decreased plasma and tissue concentrations of Fe, Cu, and Zn²⁺ by up to 15%. In addition, Sn is added to the diet as SnCl₂, concentrations up to about 200 mg Sn/kg can affect Fe, Cu and Zn²⁺ state in rats, but the effects are inconclusive [31]. Zinc act as a fundamental cofactor for the activity of up to 300 zinc-containing enzymes, including alcohol dehydrogenase, carbonic anhydrase, and superoxide dismutase [32,33].

They suggested that the extract of *P. ginseng* induces the mRNA expression of zinc transport such as ZIP4, which has been shown to promote zinc uptake into cells [34]. If food-derived factors that promote zinc absorption by targeting the intestinal zinc absorption mechanism, specifically by targeting zinc transport (ZIP4 and ZNT1), are identified, these factors may be effective in preventing zinc deficiency through the daily diet. This may indicate that *P. ginseng* affects zinc metabolism, which indirectly affects immunoglobulin production. Similarly, *p. ginseng* may be a factor involved in certain enzymatic activities, most commonly zinc [35]. Zinc acts as an antioxidant stress agent by inhibiting the oxidation of macromolecules such as DNA and proteins [36].

This observation was in agreement with a previous study that found the calcium content in the femur of rats was significantly decreased by the oral administration of SnCl₂ (3.0 mg /100 g body weight, 6 times at 12-h intervals) [37]. A previous study also reported that the administration of SnCl₂ for 3 days significantly reduced serum calcium and femoral calcium levels in rats orally given SnCl₂ (3.0mg Sn/100g body weight, every 12 hours) [6]. And this disagreement may refer to a difference in the amount of calcium between serum and femur or the dose of SnCl₂ that was used in these studies. The effect of SnCl₂ on urinary calcium concentration was studied in rats intraperitoneally administered with SnCl₂. The concentration of calcium in urine was significantly decreased by the administration of SnCl₂ (3.0 mg/100 g). The reduction of urinary calcium concentration, induced by SnCl₂, was not restored by the injection of calcium in rats treated with SnCl₂. A study was carried out by [38] referred that SnCl₂ lead to inhibit the excretion of calcium in the urine of rats. SnCl₂ has been shown to facilitate the transmitter release by promoting Ca²⁺ influx at the nerve terminals, but not by blocking the potassium channels and the mechanism of action of SnCl₂ in mice is identical to that in the frog [39]. It was demonstrated that tin, such as SnCl₂, can facilitate neuromuscular transmission by accelerating the transmitter release from the nerve terminals in the mouse. When this salt is injected into laboratory animals, it can produce stimulation or depression of the central nervous system [40].

CONCLUSION

The results obtained from the present study convincingly demonstrated that SnCl₂ exposure resulted in varying degrees of biochemical parameters in rabbits. *P. ginseng* has promise as a nutritional supplement to help prevent disorders involving SnCl₂-induced toxic effects on these parameters *P. ginseng* is a potent antioxidant due to its ability to attenuate the reactivity of ROS and to enhance the activities of detoxifying enzymes. Thus *P. ginseng* may be helpful to combat SnCl₂-associated sufferings in humans as well as animals.

Disclaimer

The article has not been previously presented or published, and is not part of a thesis project.

Conflict of Interest

There are no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest to declare.

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